

EXPERIENCE IN INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The article emphasizes the importance of innovative activities as the most important factor in improving the competitiveness of industrial complexes at the modern stage of the development of socio-economic relations. The level of scientific technological development, in turn, is considered the basis for economic growth. In support of the project for the development of the national industrial complex of each state with a developed economy, it emphasizes the emphasis on the development of innovative high-tech products. One by one, the United States, Germany, Japan, South Korea, and Finland stopped short of developing the industrial network. In conclusion, recommendations are made based on foreign experience in the innovative development of industry in our region.

Keywords: Innovative economy, export, machinery and equipment, high-tech industrial network, technological innovation, modernization, science and technology, foreign experience.

Introduction

Today, 80-95% of gross domestic product (GDP) growth in industrialized countries corresponds to new knowledge in technology and technology. The rapid development of the "new economy", the interrelationship between the capital and new technology markets, the creation of knowledge, technologies and services on a large scale form the basis for the innovative development of the region.

According to the experience of developed countries, broad innovative activity is carried out by large businesses. In the EU (EI) countries, only 80% of large enterprises and only a third of small businesses are innovative activists. For research and development, 56%, in the United States - 63%, in Japan - 74% are accounted for by the government at internal expenses. Industrial enterprises that are implementing technological innovations in developed countries account for 43.7% to 69.7% of all industrial enterprises. Therefore, it is intended to

study the world's experience in promoting innovative work in the development of regional industry.

Methods used in the study

In the process of writing the article, theoretical and practical aspects of innovative development of developed countries were compared, as well as suggestions and recommendations based on an analysis of open statistics. General research methods were used.

Scientific essence

In recent years, the "Triple Helix" model has been widely used in the innovative development of the region in theory and practice, which was proposed by American scientist Henry Iskovy, a professor at Stanford University. It emphasizes interactions between universities, businesses and the state as the cornerstone of an innovative system. He also considers the role of universities in the innovative development of regional industry to be one of the leaders. At the same time, the "Three Spirals" model constipates on the following basics:

1. Strengthening their mission in the mutual relationship between industry and government and universities in a science-based society.
2. University-business government. Efforts to interact with these three and innovative development are carried out not at the will of the government, but at the discretion of the three institutions.
3. In addition to traditional tasks, each of the three institutions performs the duties of each other in a certain sense.

According to Henry Iskovitsa, the university is not only an educational institution but also an institution that practices the knowledge accumulated. Participation of universities in the system of production and implementation of knowledge will enable the development of new technologies with other research institutions.

Currently, such universities have been named "Universities of Entrepreneurship" because many universities have their own capacity for technology transfer. For universities, laboratory to industry is one of the most efficient and safe ways to get technologies across, making it a natural drive (10% annually) for young researchers to be hired by industrial companies.

Another way to transfer new technologies are business centers, scientific technological parks, business incubators and other innovative infrastructure facilities that are organized within universities. Entrepreneurial universities use knowledge in practice, incorporate the results into new teaching subjects and participate in the development of an interactive innovative model.

Based on the aforementioned theory, the scientific nature of this research aims to identify the framework of necessary activities for the development of innovative products in the regional industry based on the experience of developed countries and to highlight the results achieved in this regard.

Results and discussion

For many years, the United States has been considered the world leader of industrial and innovative development. In the 1970s, the country developed an information mechanism for the distribution of new ideas and technologies. This activity was carried out by the National Center of the Consortium of Scientific and Technical Information and Federal Laboratories. It collects data on the results of research by all state institutions. More than 300 federal scientific centers entered the center.

Experience in the United States shows that with the support of the state for the innovative development of regional industry, a special emphasis was placed on the commercialization mechanism of innovative products and the issuance of leading technologies from the state system to the private sector for secondary use and distribution.

The policy in the field of industrial development made Germany the leader of economic development not only in Europe, but around the world. Scientific research and innovative development have fulfilled an important task for Germany's industrial complex. For German enterprises, the main objective was to implement new or better production tools and technologies, raw materials and software in a wide range of ways and quickly. In the 1980's, the main focus in the development of scientific research in Germany was on large industries in the regions. Financing for this direction accounted for 2/3 of the total cost of research and development.

In 2006, the Strategy for Innovative and Technological Development was adopted in Germany. The strategy clearly outlined the main areas of behavior in the field of national innovation and the instruments for their implementation from a regional point of view. This document identified Germany in new directions in the technological sphere, taking into account the development of science in the world. The strategy identified 17 leading industries that had an advantage over national farming. A long-term development program was developed for them.

Scientific research facilities have developed projects for the short, medium, and long-term economic development of industrial enterprises based on orders. For example, as a result of the implementation of such projects,

companies such as Volkswagen verk, Daymler Bens, Opel, and Ford were separated.

One of the leading regions in the innovative development of industry is the north Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) region of North Rhine-Westphalia. The cost to research here is around 0.2-0.3% of GDP. In the 1970's and 1980's, metallurgical companies and mines were closed due to the crisis (the reason for this was a sudden reduction in demand for coal and metal). Large-scale unemployment growth has caused a deep depression in the region. The government has designated the development of innovative technologies in the region as a way out of the problem. Regional economic policy envisioned the following components:

- formation of clearly oriented clusters in the region: biotechnology, information technology, chemistry, reconstruction of energy and resource saving resources;
- reshaping the system of training, changing the nomenclature of specialists in accordance with the chosen leading areas of science;
- formation of scientific and technological centers, allocation of equipment-equipped areas for graduates of higher educational institutions.

In Japan's economy, the state is particularly distinguished by its active intervention in industrialization policies. In Japan, the private and non-governmental sector is dominant. Japan has done the following in implementing industrial policy:

- the Export Council was formed, which coordinates the activities of all government agencies that meet export policy;
- advertising centers promoting Japanese trade have been opened in foreign countries;
- secured the production process and provided export-producing enterprises with short-term loans ahead of the export process;
- a system of discounts on exported income taxes has been introduced.

One of the most important steps was the formation of technoparks through the government in japan in the innovative development of the industry from a regional point of view. In the 1980s, the Japanese government began implementing comprehensive programs for the organization of technopolies. According to the developed "Technopolis" program, 20 technical zones named technopolis were established in districts that lag behind in individual economic development.

In the first year, companies operating in high-tech networks were allowed to calculate depreciation of basic tools by 30%, buildings and structures by 15%. The state paid for 1/3 of its joint scientific research by laboratory and small firms.

Private capital was actively involved in the organization of infrastructure of technopolies, which became a source of active integration of science and production in educational institutions. Diversity and flexibility of tax benefits for participants of industrial institutions (i.e. technopolies, clusters) have served as an important mechanism for increasing the innovative activity of enterprises of industrial complexes in the country or specific region.

It is important to study the experience of the Republic of South Korea in the innovative development of regional industry. The adoption of the first five-year plan for 1962-1966, support for export-oriented industries, influenced the innovative development of the textile, food, automotive, shipbuilding, electronics, and chemical industries. The direct assistance of the state to the creation of large industrial unions "chebols" 2 in South Korea, the allocation of state loans and foreign equipment has contributed to the widespread implementation of innovative development. South Korea has paid special attention to the development of biotechnological industries in the process of innovative industrial development.

Finland focused mainly on innovative industrial development in the 1990s. He also identified the need to identify national advantages in the allocation of limited scientific and technical resources. Over the past 20 years, investment in scientific research in Finland has more than doubled compared to the countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. In doing so, the average annual increase was 10%. Such progress was realized due to the existence of free market and active competition.

Conclusions

The experience of many of the above countries shows that clustering is one of the most effective methods of innovative development of the regional industry. But there is no single mechanism for organizing, developing and stimulating classrooms. Based on this approach, in order to modernize the economy of the region, it is necessary to develop a valid class policy program that will support the initiatives of representatives of industrial complexes in the modern economic and social climate. It is possible to define the following areas that can be implemented in support of the development of clusters:

Experience in foreign countries has shown that various means of government incentives have served as the basis for the innovative development of industry.

First, the activation of the innovative process of industrial complexes resulted in strong government support. Direct funding, grant allocation and various dotations (Japan), government orders and procurement (USA) were accounted for.

Second, world experience has shown that industrial complexes are the core of innovative development and are the basis for the growth of the entire economy. Therefore, first of all, it was necessary to create an environment to activate the process of developing high-tech networks in the region. The growth of innovative activity in most states has not taken place without government support.

Third, foreign experience has shown that innovative companies have been granted various benefits by the government, including tax credits (USA). These steps led to the recruitment of new investors to the country (region) for the implementation of innovative projects.

Fourth, world experience has shown the need for cooperation development among industrial companies, academic and educational institutions (USA, Japan, France and others). The interaction between business and science has activated the process of commercialization of existing scientific and technological developments in a short period of time. This has improved productivity.

Fifth, innovative activity was organized by implementing the regional production system (manufacturing clusters, technoparks and technopolies). Increasing production efficiency envisioned the formation of a chain of cooperation: from the start of the mining company to the customer within a region, a link has arisen between the company that supplies the product.

Sixth, world experience has shown important results in the strategy for innovative development of ITTKIs, bringing the share of ITTKI-oriented expenses to 3%, bringing investment volumes to 30%, achieving a bachelor's degree in at least 60% of young people, and government financing of ITTKIs.

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